

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B SYNERGIES STRATEGY

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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The report includes mapped synergies with regional and international fora building on existing cooperation e.g. with Eklipse, Oppla, Science Service, Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, and on-going and planned Horizon Europe projects addressing climate and biodiversity challenges and transformative changes. Other international or national initiatives and projects on behavioural science, intersectionality, gender, climate change and biodiversity will also be mapped and featured along with steps how to approach and cooperate with them.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DEAR	Development, Education and Awareness Raising
GD	Good Issue Ltd.
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIFE	L'Instrument Financier pour l'Environnement
M(6)	Month (six)
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
TCBPI database	Transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives database
UNEP-WCMC	United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

- The objective of this synergies strategy is to set out how cooperation with other projects and initiatives may take place to maximise existing synergies and increase PLANET4B's impact.
- This strategy describes the different types of external projects and initiatives that PLANET4B can collaborate with, as well as outlining a timeline and management of activities.
- This document also sets out a seven-step process for identifying synergies with a repertoire of existing projects and initiatives with similar focus.
- Collaboration will be informed by the PLANET4B transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives database (PLANET4B TCBPI database) developed within the project (Task 5.3).
- Overall, over 70 projects and initiatives have been identified as potentially relevant for synergy, and will provide the base for joint actions, while mapping of additional synergies with emerging projects and initiatives will continuously be undertaken.
- Collaboration between projects and initiatives will seek to produce results that are greater than what projects could achieve on their own, with the aim to maximise reach, impact and potential uptake in prioritisation of biodiversity in decision making.

1 Introduction

PLANET4B is a Horizon Europe project, under the transformative change for biodiversity cluster, that seeks to understand intersectionality, behaviour and the motivations around biodiversity prioritisation in decision making through transdisciplinary research. The project has two primary objectives. Firstly, the project seeks to understand how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect, and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision making across a range of different scales and settings. Secondly, the project seeks to channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted (yet, scalable) policy recommendations, in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss. Given this broad scope of topics, transdisciplinary nature of the research and the policy implications of the project, PLANET4B lends itself to many different types of synergies-based collaboration with external partners. The aim of fostering collaboration with other projects based on shared synergies is to increase the impact and reach of PLANET4B while allowing space for other projects and initiatives with similar focus and objectives to provide input and increase joint impact.

This document lays out a strategy for PLANET4B to follow to collaborate with similar projects and initiatives throughout and beyond the lifecycle of the project. The strategy, amongst other things, seeks to define different types of collaboration, provide an outline of what types of projects and initiatives to collaborate with, define goals and a timeline for collaboration and communicate specific steps to the PLANET4B consortium to follow for identifying synergies and collaboration with other projects and initiatives. Accordingly, for the consortium partners, the primary focus of this synergies strategy is to act as an internal guidance document for partners within PLANET4B. However, this strategy document also works as an open invitation for external partners

to identify synergies with PLANET4B and reach out to us to establish ways of growing our impact through joint collaborative activities. In this sense, the synergies strategy will be a living document that will be continuously updated for which we actively seek input from external partners through our collaboration actions.

1.1 Background

To date, limited knowledge exists on concurrent projects and initiatives focusing on transformative change for biodiversity. To bridge this knowledge gap through an inventory and to enhance PLANET4B's impacts through cooperation, this synergies strategy has been developed. This synergies strategy document constitutes one of the deliverables (D5.5) of Task 5.3 *Mapping synergies and creating cooperation with existing initiatives and projects* led by UNEP-WCMC within the context of the PLANET4B project. This synergies strategy will form the basis for collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects under and beyond the same cluster¹ as well as other EU and non-EU funded projects and initiatives that have synergies with PLANET4B themes. An integral part of the strategy is the PLANET4B transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives database TCBPI which acts as a repertoire of projects and initiatives (see Annex I) that deal with relevant topics to those addressed by PLANET4B.

Not only does the PLANET4B TCBPI database seek to respond to this knowledge gap, it is also highly relevant to PLANET4B's attempt to synthesise and build upon transdisciplinary knowledge. To be released in M6 of the project cycle, the PLANET4B synergies strategy aims to foster cross-fertilization of knowledge and outcomes and strengthen partnerships between projects and initiatives that have a focus on transformative change for biodiversity decision making. This document will be regularly reviewed based on feedback received from consortium members and external partners, and a new updated version of the deliverable will be published in M30 (D5.6).

1.2 Objectives

This synergies strategy has a twofold objective. **The first objective** is to map and record existing projects and initiatives that address topics similar to those investigated within the PLANET4B in the TCBPI database (Annex I). Such similar topics may relate to, but are not limited to, gender, intersectionality, behaviour and transformation within the context of biodiversity and more broadly environmental governance. This repository of projects and initiatives acts as a starting point for assessing the specific synergistic complementarity with work carried out by PLANET4B. **The second objective** is to formulate a process and timeline that will guide how collaboration to maximise synergies with other projects and initiatives can take place. Collaboration with external projects and initiatives will seek to leverage synergies around different *types* of cooperation (to be identified later on when contacting the projects and initiatives):

- **Knowledge sharing:** The sharing of knowledge generated by PLANET4B project activities with other projects or initiatives which includes ensuring that PLANET4B knowledge is capitalised on and built into other future projects.

¹ A specific deliverable (D5.11) for establishing a joint work plan for collaboration with Horizon Europe projects under the transformative change for biodiversity cluster will be developed for M9.

- **Knowledge co-production:** Working with other projects on joint research/knowledge creation activities on common areas of investigation for the creation/extension of joint products.
- **Common dissemination and communication:** Creating common dissemination, communication and exploitation activities with other projects.
- **Actions leading to future collaboration:** Working to create activities that will hold a focus on future work that may go beyond the lifespan of the projects to ensure the sustainability of the project's results and extend the reach and impact of the project.

2 Definitions and steps for identifying synergies and coordinating collaboration with external partners

To provide a structure to the process of collaboration with similar projects and initiatives based on common areas of work, this synergies strategy outlines a step-by-step process to follow. In sum, this is as follows:

- 1 Identify and map similar projects and initiatives (see Annex I, a living database which will be regularly reviewed and updated until M30).
- 2 Assess synergistic complementarity.
- 3 Contact synergistic projects and initiatives.
- 4 Coordinate and implement collaborative activities.
- 5 Communicate and disseminate.
- 6 Monitor and report.
- 7 Set future collaboration.

Steps for identifying synergies and coordinating collaboration

Figure 1. Steps for identifying synergies and coordinating collaboration with external projects and initiatives. Source: Justine Lancelin.

These steps will be conducted iteratively in collaboration with PLANET4B partners and external projects and initiatives. Collaboration will be undertaken with the aim of building mutual trust through honest and inclusive dialogues with involved stakeholders that ensure favourable conditions and outcomes for all involved (Pettersson & Hrelja, 2020). This strategy defines a project to mean an enterprise that has been funded and planned to achieve a particular aim. In comparison, this strategy understands an

initiative to take a broader meaning relating to broader schemes, campaigns, organisations and networks that are planned to achieve a particular aim.

2.1 Identify and map similar projects and initiatives

This initial step is key to meeting the first objective of the synergies strategy, to map and record existing projects and initiatives investigating themes similar to PLANET4B in a database. A first iteration of the PLANET4B TCBPI database to record existing projects and initiatives relevant to PLANET4B has been completed. This database can be found in Annex I and will be continuously updated, as set out in the timeline.

The methodology behind the creation of the PLANET4B TCBPI database was conceived from an initial review of the CORDIS project database website and a review of the OpenAIRE Explore project database website through keyword searches to identify and record projects and initiatives of relevance. The CORDIS project website was selected as it is “the primary source of results from EU projects since 1990” (European Commission, 2023) whereas OpenAIRE Explore was selected because it operates as an extensive open dataset linking 3 million different grants to 197 thousand organisations (OpenAIRE, 2023)

The primary keywords used for the keyword searches are as follows: “Biodiversity” and “Climate change”. The secondary key words were: “Behavioural Science” OR “behavioral science”, “Intersectionality”, “Gender”, “Ethnicity”, “Leverage points”, “Attitudes”, “Creative methods”, “Transformative change”, “Theory”, “Social theory”, “Behavioural theory” OR “behavioral theory”, “Social science”, “Behavioural intervention” OR “behavioral intervention”, “Behavioural change” OR “behavioral change”, “Nudging”, “Degrowth”, “Institutional change”, “Psychology”, “Decision-making”, “Decision-making intervention”. The PLANET4B TCBPI database was then reviewed by partner organisations within the consortium who – based on their expert knowledge – added additional projects and initiatives of relevance that PLANET4B may plausibly be able to collaborate with. The above keywords were selected based on their relevance to the themes of PLANET4B. Further keywords including more alterations and synonyms will be additionally included and tested to identify gaps and to complement the database by M9.

2.2 Assess synergistic complementarity

The TCBPI database provides a reference point to assess synergistic complementarity between PLANET4B and the relevant project or initiative in question working as a starting point to conduct further research into the identified project or initiative. This will involve an assessment of the materials within the project or initiative’s website as well as other accessible materials that may relate to common work areas or potential for cross-fertilization. This information will then be recorded in an extended database listing the specific topic of the project/initiative and envisioned type of co-operation.

2.3 Contact synergistic projects and initiatives

If it is determined that there is potential for collaboration then the external project or initiative will be contacted. A meeting (virtual or in person) will be set to discuss synergistic areas of work and potential for collaboration between PLANET4B and the

external project or initiative. The conversation will be organised around the following topics:

- Brief introduction of PLANET4B and the relevant project or initiative
- Joint mapping of co-operation and collaboration points
- Potential joint activities and outcomes
- Target group identification and potential common communication and dissemination actions
- Setting timeframe and concrete next steps
- Mapping any other potential co-operation and collaboration partners to involve

In engaging with these topics, the collaboration meeting will also address how the collaboration will be set up and maintained (e.g. through what communication channels, frequency of potential check-ins) and who will be the specific contact points on both sides of the collaboration.

2.4 Coordinate and implement collaborative activities

Once contact has been made with the partner organisation, the specific coordination activities and implementation of actions will be determined by the PLANET4B partners and the external partners based on their needs and available resources for the work, including input from the lead for Task 5.3. Any decisions about financing should be discussed with the WP lead and the co-coordinators or through the PLANET4B Steering Committee before resource intensive collaboration is agreed on.

The implementation of collaborative activities within PLANET4B will be either delegated to the relevant consortium partner with oversight from UNEP-WCMC or directly implemented by UNEP-WCMC. The decision making for determining the process by which who specifically will carry out the implementation of the agreed upon collaboration will relate to the *type* of cooperation (as outlined in section 1.2) and its relevance to specific tasks being carried out by PLANET4B partners.

2.5 Communicate and disseminate

Upon agreement to collaborate with an external project or initiative, communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be decided with the WP5 lead (GD) to match the type of collaboration that will take place. Types of communication and dissemination activities that could, depending on what is appropriate, accompany different forms of collaboration with external partners include:

- Joint social media communication activities promoting cooperation and results of cooperation
- Promotion of joint events or workshops through different communication outlets available
- Outreach to media organisations, including the joint drafting of press releases
- Shared web-based communication, including uploading content or articles to the relevant websites.

2.6 Monitor and report

The strategy and its TCBPI database will constitute a living document updated regularly between M6–M30 through updates from the Task lead and partners. By M12 a stock-take of the resources and impact of collaborating with projects and initiatives that have been contacted will be made. Specific reporting on co-operation will also be required from partners every 6-months through the project and WP5 reporting as well as relevant project meetings (WP5 meeting, WP leads meeting, Steering Committee meeting). Here, partners report on the steps of cooperation in a reporting template (e.g. on whether contact has taken place, type of co-operation established, concrete activities, outputs). Informed by this, an updated synergies strategy (D5.6) will be compiled by M30. An existing key performance indicator (KPI) for the PLANET4B project will be used to monitor the progress of collaborating with EU projects. This KPI is as follows: Number of actions relating to joint actions with other EU projects (e.g. joint events, joint communication). KPI: Number of joint actions (target: 10). The synergies strategy and its activities will likely contribute to further PLANET4B KPIs, as well.

2.7 Set future collaboration

The final step will relate to exploring the potential for future collaboration beyond the lifespan of PLANET4B to ensure the sustainability of the projects results and extend the reach and impact of the project. Discussing future collaboration with external partners may take the form of building on the results of PLANET4B through future project proposals or creation of networks, ensuring its knowledge is directly provided to new projects and initiatives.

3 External projects and initiatives to build synergies with

PLANET4B will seek to collaborate with different types of projects and initiatives through the seven-step process. A first round of mapping and recording these different types of projects and initiatives has been undertaken (see step 2.1 above), which resulted in the following five categories.

3.1 International projects and initiatives beyond Europe

A particular effort will be made to render PLANET4B project results usable for IPBES and IPCC. This will include a consortium level effort to provide review comments for the IPBES' Nexus assessment, Transformative change assessment and Business and biodiversity assessment along with the future IPBES and IPCC report. PLANET4B is currently further exploring ways to contribute to intergovernmental assessment reports through the PLANET4B experts who are participating in these processes. Moreover, many projects and initiatives listed in the PLANET4B TCBPI database will have an international component (beyond Europe) to them. Collaboration with projects and initiatives of global relevance that contribute to achieving international goals such as the SDGs will also fall under this category.

3.2 European initiatives

PLANET4B will aim to foster collaboration with appropriate regional and European fora. Initiatives such as Eklipse, the European Biodiversity Partnership (Biodiversa+),

Oppla, Science Service and the Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity of the European Commission will be contacted and existing partnerships between PLANET4B partner organisations and these initiatives will endeavour to be built on.

3.3 Horizon Europe projects from transformative change for biodiversity cluster

PLANET4B will seek to create and encourage strong cooperation based on shared synergies with Horizon Europe projects under the transformative change for biodiversity cluster². A separate deliverable (D5.11) will be developed relating to this for M9. This action plan will produce mapped synergies and relevant actions with the Horizon Europe transformative change cluster projects, including, but not limited to, drawing from the in-person first cluster event in March 2023 where representatives from the 11 Horizon Europe projects met.

3.4 Other Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects

PLANET4B partners will also pursue cooperative relationships based on shared synergies with other similar Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects outside of the transformative change for biodiversity cluster. This includes projects such as BioAgora, the Cooperation for the Convention on Biological Diversity and the NetworkNature. This effort to will also drive the development of partnerships with Horizon Europe projects that started in 2019, 2020 or 2021 which will be more advanced in the lifecycle of their project than PLANET4B. Reading, analysing and building on the results of these slightly older projects will also be coordinated under task 5.3. In addition, and as outlined in section 1.2, PLANET4B will also seek to cooperate with Horizon Europe projects that are to be funded in future calls, making sure they build on PLANET4B results. The PLANET4B TCBPI database and the synergies strategy will be updated to include these.

3.5 Other relevant projects and initiatives

Separately from seeking to foster collaborations based on synergies with Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects and other international projects and initiatives, PLANET4B will try to develop collaborative relationships with other relevant projects and initiatives. This includes other EU-funded projects (e.g. funded by LIFE, DEAR or Interreg mechanisms) as well as local or national non-EU funded projects and initiatives that have been added to PLANET4B TCBPI database.

4 Timeline and management of activities

4.1 Management Activities

Task 5.3 will map synergies with other projects and initiatives as well as undertake a programme of reaching out and collaborating with these external partners. As task lead for task 5.3, UNEP-WCMC is responsible for the oversight and good management of

² Besides PLANET4B, the other Horizon Europe projects under the transformative change for biodiversity cluster are as follows: BAMBOO, BIONEXT, BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BioValue, CLEVER, RAINFOREST, SUSTAIN, TC4BE, TRANSPATH. For the full project names, see Annex I.

the synergies strategy. However, the activities relating to certain forms of collaboration around shared knowledge production and co-production of knowledge will be discussed and distributed to the relevant PLANET4B partners. UNEP-WCMC will carry out the work of contacting the external projects and initiatives unless otherwise agreed upon with PLANET4B partners or if the collaboration relates to knowledge co-creation or the co-production of work relating to a deliverable relevant to another PLANET4B partner organisation. If the latter is the case, this PLANET4B partner organisation will oversee contact with the external partner but will keep the lead for Task 5.3 in copy for any relevant correspondences.

The management of activities for certain forms of collaboration that will have a foreseeable resource requirement relating to labour and finances will also determine how joint activities can be realised. The relevant decision making bodies of the project, as well as the WP5 lead, will discuss and address these additional requirements where relevant, and agree on viability of implementation.

Identifying and building on synergies between PLANET4B and other projects will follow the step-by-step process laid out above in section 2 above. Exploiting synergies to maximise impact between PLANET4B and other projects and initiatives will be determined through meetings (step 2.3), both virtual or in person, with members of external projects or initiatives. When possible, in-person meetings will be sought between representatives of PLANET4B and other projects and initiatives, making the best of joint events to discuss further opportunities for jointly working on synergistic activities.

4.2 Timeline

As laid out in step 1 of the steps to coordinate collaborations with external partners, an initial mapping process to catalogue relevant projects and initiatives has already been undertaken (see Annex I). Between M6 and M12 Task 5.3 will evaluate the entries in the PLANET4B TCBPI database and run additional searches using an extended string of keywords and identify projects and initiatives that have the most synergistic complementarity with PLANET4B (step 2). Contact with external partners will begin to be made within the context of Task 5.3 between M6 and M12 where projects and initiatives with the most synergistic complementarity will be reached out to first (as outlined in Table 1 below). By M12 an evaluation and stock-take of the resources and impact of collaborating with projects and initiatives that have been contacted will be made. Therefore, although projects and initiatives deemed most relevant to PLANET4B will be reached out to between M6 and M12, contact to establish collaborative relationships with relevant projects will continue to M30. Special consideration will be given to new Horizon Europe projects and highly relevant initiatives that begin during the lifetime of PLANET4B and therefore were not yet recorded in the initial collection of projects and initiatives.

A joint workplan will be established by M9 under a separate deliverable (D5.11) which will provide an action plan to include mapped synergies and relevant actions with the Horizon Europe transformative change cluster. Co-creation of this plan will be fostered between M6 and M9 through the use of the coordinator role that the lead for Task 5.3 will play within the context of the 'norms, values and justice' working group, as well as participating in the other two working groups within the cluster. This joint workplan will

then feed into the second objective of this synergies strategy, constituting a further opportunity to maximise synergies between PLANET4B and other projects.

Throughout the project, during WP leads meetings and at other relevant internal meetings, WP leads, Task leads and partners will be reminded of the steps to follow for identifying synergies and collaboration with other projects. This reminder will include a notification that they can lead collaborations relating to knowledge sharing and co-production or joint activities relating to work that may be relevant to their deliverables (with the oversight of the Task 5.3 lead) and in consultation with relevant decision making bodies of PLANET4B. By M30, an updated synergies strategy (D5.6) will be created, informed by a review of the synergies strategy.

Table 1. Timeline and core activities of the synergies strategy.

Timeframe	Activities
M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Published synergies strategy Begin reaching out to projects with the highest synergetic complementarity with PLANET4B until M12
Continuously (every six months from M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revise synergies strategy Revise PLANET4B TCBPI database
M9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish Action Plan of Transformative Change Clustering (D5.11) Develop an extended version of the PLANET4B TCBPI database
M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stocktake of existing collaborations and revised plan and continue contacting external partners listed in PLANET4B TCBPI database until M30
M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish updated synergies strategy (D5.6)

5 Conclusion and next steps

Mapping projects and initiatives that address similar thematic areas is an ongoing process. The process of collaboration with external partners will seek to identify synergies (i.e. overlapping or adjacent work) between projects and initiatives, coordinating joint activities and exploiting these synergies through different types of cooperation, such as knowledge sharing, knowledge co-creation, common communication and dissemination activities, along with planning future collaboration.

Regarding next steps, a rolling set of activities will be conducted as part of task 5.3. These are as follows:

- Assessing synergistic complementarity of projects and initiatives in the PLANET4B TCBPI database and reaching out to external partners between M6 and M12. Part of this work will inform the creation of an Action Plan of Transformative Change Clustering with the Horizon Europe Transformative Change cluster projects (D5.11) for M9.
- Revising and extending the search for developing a systematic version of the PLANET4B TCBPI database (for example by adding more relevant keywords and their derivatives) and regularly update the database

- Coordinating and implementing collaboration actions between M6–M30
- Encouraging other partner organisations within the PLANET4B consortium to follow the steps laid out for coordinating collaborations with external partners.

Through the steps, delegation of work and activities laid out above, PLANET4B will provide an inventory of relevant projects and initiatives bridging the gap, ensure its knowledge is directly provided to new projects and initiatives as well as seek to maximise its reach and impact through collaboration with external partners on shared synergies.

References

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- Pettersson, F. & Hrelja, R. (2020). How to create functioning collaboration in theory and in practice—practical experiences of collaboration when planning public transport systems. *International journal of sustainable transportation*, 14(1), 1–13.
- OpenAIRE (2023). Discover open linked research. Available at: <https://explore.openaire.eu/> (accessed April 18, 2023).

Statement on data availability

Some data used to generate the task PLANET4B TCBPI database were accessed from two online open access repositories of projects and initiatives. These are [OpenAIRE Explore](#) and [CODRIS](#).

Statement on ethics

The content described in this synergies strategy has been developed fully based on publicly accessible repositories and there were no ethical considerations. The contact information relating to projects and initiatives in the PLANET4B TCBPI database in Annex I are all taken from open access websites in the public domain.

Annex

PLANET4B transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives (TCBPI) database

Abbreviation of the project/initiative	Full title of the project	Project/initiative	PLANET4B partner leading synergies work	Relevant project link	Project contact
Access to Justice for a Greener Europe	Access to Justice for a Greener Europe	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/access-to-justice-for-a-greener-europe/#updates	info@justiceandenvironment.org
ACCTING	AdvanCing behavioural Change Through an INclusive Green deal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://accting.eu/join-the-network/	accting-eu@esf.org
Are Religions becoming Green?	Are Religions becoming Green?	Project	FIBL	https://greenreligion.theologie.unibas.ch/de/are-religions-becoming-green/	https://greenreligion.theologie.unibas.ch/de/kontakt/
Bamboo	Biodiversity and trade: mitigating the impacts of non-food biomass and global supply chains	Project	SRU	https://bamboo-horizon.eu/	https://bamboo-horizon.eu/contact.html
Basic Needs and Intergenerational Climate Justice	Basic Needs and Intergenerational Climate Justice	Project	CAC	https://basicneeds.uni-graz.at/en/the-project/	lukas.meyer@uni-graz.at

BEATLES	Co-creating Behavioural Change Towards Climate Smart Food Systems	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://beatles-project.eu/	info@beatles-project.eu
BESTMAP	Behavioural, Ecological and socio-economic tools for modelling agricultural policy	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bestmap.eu/	g.ziv@leeds.ac.uk
BiNatUr	Bringing Nature Back – biodiversity-friendly nature-based solutions in cities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bringingnatureback.com/	kati.vierikko@syke.fi
BioAgora	Connecting biodiversity knowledge and decision making	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bioagora.eu/	https://bioagora.eu/contact/
BIOCONSENT	Decision-making Support for Forest Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration Policy and Management in Europe: Trade-offs and Synergies at the Forest-Biodiversity-Climate-Water Nexus	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/biodivrestore/biodivrestore-transnational-cofund-call-2021/decision-making-support-for-forest-biodiversity-conservation-and-restoration-policy-and-management-in-europe-trade-offs-and-synergies-at-the-forest-biodiversity-climate-water-nexus	https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/biodivrestore/biodivrestore-transnational-cofund-call-2021/decision-making-support-for-forest-biodiversity-conservation-and-restoration-policy-and-management-in-europe-trade-offs-and-synergies-at-the-forest-biodiversity-climate-water-nexus
Biodiversa+	The European Biodiversity Partnership	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biodiversa.eu/	https://www.biodiversa.eu/contact/

BioNext	The Biodiversity Nexus – Triggering Transformative Change for Sustainability (BIONEXT)	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.bionext-project.eu/	bionext.project@syke.fi
BIOTraces	Biodiversity and transformative change for plural and nature-positive societies	Project	SRU	https://www.biotraces.eu/	rosalie.vandam@wur.nl
BioTrails	Nexus Framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://biotrailsproject.eu/	https://biotrailsproject.eu/contact-us/
BioValue	Biodiversity value in spatial policy and planning leveraging multi-level and transformative change	Project	NINA	https://biovalue-horizon.eu/	https://biovalue-horizon.eu/contacts/
BLUEPRINT	BLUEPRINT to a Circular Economy	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://projectblueprint.eu/	https://projectblueprint.eu/partners
CAMPAIGNERS	Citizens Acting on Mitigation Pathways through Active Implementation of a Goal-setting Network	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.climate-campaigners.com/Global#rewards	https://project.climate-campaigners.com/Contact
CAOP	Climate Adaptation for Older People Living in Vulnerable Urban Areas: Designing a Climate-responsive and community-based methodology	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://citta.fe.up.pt/projects/1-81-caop-climate-adaptation-for-older-people-living-in-vulnerable-urban-areas-designing-a-climate-responsive-and-community-based-methodology	https://citta.fe.up.pt/projects/1-81-caop-climate-adaptation-for-older-people-living-in-vulnerable-urban-areas-designing-a-climate-responsive-and-community-based-methodology
CLEVER	Creating Leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade	Project	SRU	https://clever-project.eu/	Communications Officer: Rosa Castañeda

					rosa.castaneda@efi.int
Co-creating and applying a theory of change for biodiversity credits	Co-creating and applying a theory of change for biodiversity credits – towards a nature-positive future	Project	UNEP-WCMC	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX016315%2F1	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX016315%2F1
COEVOLVERS	Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.uni-erfurt.de/en/research/researching/research-projects/coevolvers	carsten.herrmann-pillath@uni-erfurt.de
COOP4CBD	Cooperation for the Convention on Biological Diversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://twitter.com/coop4cbd	https://twitter.com/coop4cbd
DECIPHER	Decision-making framework and processes for holistic evaluation of environmental and climate policies	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://globalclimateforum.org/portfolio-item/decipher/	helen.laubenstein@globalclimateforum.org
Digital Disruption and the Future of Conservation	Digital Disruption and the Future of Conservation	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://unearthodox.org/2022/06/digital-disruption-and-the-future-of-conservation/	info@unearthodox.org
DISES	Between maintenance and transformation: a socio-environmental systems framework for restoration decision-making under climate change	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=2108002	jmantz@nsf.gov

Eclipse	Eclipse	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://eclipse.eu/	https://eclipse.eu/contact/
EmpowerUS	Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://empowerus-project.eu/	mbj@norsk.no
ENFASYS	Encouraging farmers towards sustainable farming systems through policy and business	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.enfasyproject.eu/	https://www.enfasyproject.eu/contact/
EU-China Environment Project	EU-China Environment Project	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/eu-china-environment-project/#abouttheproject	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/eu-china-environment-project/#abouttheproject
EVOCLIM	Behavioral-evolutionary analysis of climate policy: Bounded rationality, markets and social interactions	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.uab.cat/doc/EVOCLIM_PROJECT_AND_ITS_RESULTS_EN	https://www.ivanvsavin.org/about
FRESH	Farmer acceptable Restoration of Semi-natural Habitat to limit Herbicides	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biodiversitysa.eu/2022/10/25/fresh/	david.bohan@inrae.fr
GenDecCCR	Gendering and Decolonising Climate Change Research: Exploring the Waterberg, South Africa	Project	NINA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023502	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023502
GENERATE	Gender, Generation and Climate Change: Creative Approaches to Building Inclusive and Resilient Cities in Uganda and Myanmar	Project	FUG	https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=MR%2FS015299%2F1	https://gtr.ukri.org/person/EECFB85C-8835-4446-A089-B5E71DA0F278

GUARDEN	SafeGUARDing biodivErsity aNd critical ecosystem services across sectors and scales	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://guarden.org/	https://guarden.org/contact-us/
INCENTIVE	Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://incentive-project.eu/about/incentive-goals/	info@incentive-project.eu
Interlace	International cooperation to restore and connect urban environments in Latin America and Europe	Project	FUG	https://www.interlace-project.eu/	https://www.interlace-project.eu/contact
IPCJ	The International People's Platform for Climate Justice	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://ourclimateimpact.org/	https://ourclimateimpact.org/contact-us/
JustFutures	Climate Futures and Just Transformations: Young People's Narratives and Political Imaginaries	Project	CAC	https://justfutures.pt/en/home-en/	carlamalafaia@fpce.up.pt
Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity	Knowledge Centre for biodiversity of the European Commission	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/biodiversity_en	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/biodiversity/about_en
Local Nature Innovation Fund	Local Nature Innovation Fund	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://experiments.friendsoftheearth.uk/projects/local-nature-innovation-fund-supporting-nature-projects-grassroots	https://r1.dotdigital-pages.com/p/78W4-6J3/contact-experiments-team?origin=is1
Mapping for good	Mapping for good	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.kartevonmorgen.org/en	https://blog.vonmorgen.org/en/contact/
MOCHA	Understanding and leveraging 'moments of change' for pro-environmental behaviour shifts	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.cardiff.ac.uk/psychology/research/impact/mom	whitmarshle@cardiff.ac.uk

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Net Zero	Net Zero Climate	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://netzeroclimate.org/	https://netzeroclimate.org/contact-us/
Network Nature	Network Nature	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://networknature.eu/	https://networknature.eu/helpdesk
Oppla	Oppla	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://oppla.eu/	https://oppla.eu/contacts
PASTOPRAXIS	Local adaptative responses of pastoralism to climate change in the Natural Park of Montesinho Portugal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://pastopraxis.cimo.ipb.pt/pastopraxis/web/index.php?r=site%2Findex&language=pt#inicio	marina.castro@ipb.pt
People, rice and mangroves at the margins	People, rice and mangroves at the margins: A hybrid and contested interface in a changing world	Project	SRU	https://www.ces.uc.pt/en/investigacao/projetos-de-investigacao/projetos-financiados/margins	https://www.ces.uc.pt/en/investigacao/projetos-de-investigacao/projetos-financiados/margins
PLAN'EAT	PLAN'EAT	Project	FIBL	https://planeat-project.eu/	https://planeat-project.eu/contact/
PLUS change	Planning land use strategies: meeting biodiversity, climate and social objectives in a changing world	Project	CG	https://www.czechglobe.cz/en/projects/?project=PLUS&provider=0&year_from=&year_to=	CG partners

Rainforest	Co-produced transformative knowledge to accelerate change for biodiversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://rainforest-horizon.eu/index.html	https://rainforest-horizon.eu/contact.html
RELATE	Environmental Spaces and the Feel-Good Factor: Relating Subjective Wellbeing to Biodiversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/726104	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/726104
RURALIZATION	The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://ruralization.eu/	https://ruralization.eu/contact/
SCALAR	Scaling up behavior and autonomous adaptation for macro models of climate change damage assessment	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://europepmc.org/grantfinder/grantdetails?query=pi%3A%22Filatova%20T%22%20qid%3A%22758014%22%20ga%3A%22European%20Research%20Council%22	T.Filatova@utwente.nl
SELINA	Science for Evidence-Based and Sustainable Decisions about Natural Capital	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://project-selina.eu/	burkhard@phygeo.uni-hannover.de
Shared Green Deal	Shared Green Deal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sharedgreendeal.eu/	chris.foulds@aru.ac.uk rosie.robison@aru.ac.uk
SSH CENTRE	Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy and Transport Research Excellence	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sshcentre.eu/	chris.foulds@aru.ac.uk rosie.robison@aru.ac.uk

StartClim	StartClim	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://startclim.at/startseite	https://startclim.at/kontakt
SUSTAIN	Strengthening Understanding and Strategies of business to Assess and Integrate Nature	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://capitalscoalition.org/project/sustain-project/	info@capitalscoalition.org
TC4BE	Transformative Change in Telecoupled Agrofood Systems for Biodiversity and Equity	Project	UNIFI	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082057	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082057
The Concept of Vulnerability in the Context of Human Rights	The Concept of Vulnerability in the Context of Human Rights	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://gmr.lbg.ac.at/projects/project-the-concept-of-vulnerability-in-the-context-of-human-rights/?lang=en	monika.mayrhofer@gmr.lbg.ac.at
The Future of Conservation NGOs	The Future of Conservation NGOs	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://unearthodox.org/2022/12/future-of-conservation-ngos/	info@unearthodox.org
TIME4CS	Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.time4cs.eu/about	time4cs@apre.it
Together for 1.5	Together for 1.5: Accelerate Climate Action in Europe	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://1point5.caneurope.org/	https://1point5.caneurope.org/contact/
TRANSCLIM	Transformative Transparency? Assessing the Effects of Reporting and Review in the International Climate Change Regime	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sites.uef.fi/cc-eel/transclim/	https://sites.uef.fi/cc-eel/transclim/

Transformations Community	Transformations Community	Initiative	CG	https://www.transformationscommunity.org/	https://www.transformationscommunity.org/contact-us
Transformative Pathways	Transformative Pathways	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.forestpeoples.org/en/transformative-pathways#:~:text=Transformative%20Pathways%20is%20a%20joint%20initiative%20led%20by%20recognising%20and%20expanding%20contributions%20by%20indigenous%20peoples.	https://www.forestpeoples.org/en/contact
TRANS-lighthouses	More than green – Lighthouses of transformative nature-based solutions for inclusive communities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://portal.research.lu.se/sv/projects/more-than-green-lighthouses-of-transformative-nature-based-soluti	ana.mm.arroz@uac.pt
Transpath	Transformative pathways for synergising just biodiversity and climate actions	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=50052	Sindy Bleiholder Phone: +49 341 235-1250 sekces@ufz.de
ValMaB – DM	Valuing Marine Biodiversity for use in Decision Making	Project	UNEP-WCMC	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pco	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pco

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ValueChange	Design for changing values: a theory of value change in sociotechnical systems	Project	NINA	https://www.valuechange.eu/	info@valuechange.eu
Wageningen Biodiversity Initiative	Wageningen Biodiversity Initiative	Initiative	MLU	https://www.wur.nl/en/themes/biodiversity/what-is-the-wageningen-biodiversity-initiative.html	https://www.futuredynamics.global/likesje-mommer-liesje-mommer-leading-the-wageningen-biodiversity-initiative-professor-plant-ecology-nature-conservation-at-wageningen-university-research/?print=print
WOW	The Writing's on the Wall	Project	CAC	https://thewritingsonthewall.org/	hello@thewritingsonthewall.org